

A REVIEW OF MANAGEMENT AND PROJECT PLANNING IN CONSTRUCTION INDUSTRY

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ABSTRACT:

The construction industries are continuously growing since the last decade with the globalization. Success of any construction industry is dependent on the quality and timely delivery of the construction projects. Before thinking to start any construction project, decision makers have to prepare a complete plan for successful completion of project. Project planning and proper management leads to the success of any construction industry. It was observed that, the construction projects mainly delayed due to inappropriate planning and bad management. While planning any project one need to consider various factors affecting success of project and has to forecast the future problems too. Construction project management mainly deals with, manpower, funds, material, authorization from the government authorities, legal permissions and better coordination. In this paper, authors have carried out and extensive review of the opinions presented by the researchers.

KEYWORDS: Construction, Project Planning, Project Management, Risk Management.

INTRODUCTION:

The figure drawn below shows the overview of the project planning needed for the success of any construction project. The construction planning mainly done on the basis of cost and scheduled delivery, planner has to think of the factor for planning and forecasting. Authors have presented the literature survey on the opinions of different researcher on the construction management and planning.

If one is willing to reduce the cost then it is highly impossible to deliver the project at scheduled time and vice versa. In considering the cost oriented planning the direct and indirect costs belongs to the project are to be considered. While thinking of the scheduled delivery of project, the resources are to be

made available as and when required, cost of the resources doesn't matter in this case.

In the management of the construction projects, various factors are to be considered such as the material, labor, daily activities, funds, accounting, and smooth conduction of projects. Mismanagement of any one of the stated factors will result in the overrun of cost or delay in project. The construction project starts with planning, research for the land, acquisition of the land, resource availability etc.

Fig.1: Overview of Planning

In the management of the construction projects, various factors are to be considered such as the material, labor, daily activities, funds, accounting, and smooth conduction of projects. Mismanagement of any one of the stated factors will result in the overrun of cost or delay in project. The construction project starts with planning, research for the land, acquisition of the land, resource availability etc.

The construction industry is contributing continuously to the GDP of the developing countries. In India, it has provided considerable employment

opportunities. The role of construction industries have changed just from completion of project to improvement of quality and producing the sustainable construction. With the use of computers and software's, it has become very easy to build the project map. Software's are available to support the construction industries there by providing the total analysis of the project and forecasting the risks related to projects. Apart from the cost and time one of the important factors is customer's satisfaction.

FACTORS AFFECTING THE CONSTRUCTION PROJECT:

- Review
- Planning
- Land
- Design
- Labor
- Finance
- Material
- Forecast
- Sustainability
- Risk identification
- Market conditions
- Management
- Other resources

LITERATURE SURVEY:

Mansfield, Nigel R., O. O. Ugwu, and T. Doran et.al have presented the reasons and causes of delay in the delivery of construction projects from the point of view of construction industries in Nigeria. In this paper the data of various construction projects are discussed. From the data of the projects the causes of cost overruns have been discussed. Main focus of the study is on the highway projects completed on Nigeria. The remedies to reduce the failure of timely delivery and cost overrun are discussed in the paper [1].

Laufer, Alexander, and Richard L. Tucker et.al has presented the overview of the project planning from the point of view of the construction industry. Authors have proposed that, the resources are available but the planning is improper hence the projects are delayed. The paper focused on the myth versus the reality in completion of the project. Project handling is an art of human being [2].

Warszawski, Abraham et.al has discussed about the strategic planning for the construction companies. The importance of the strategic planning in the construction industry has been discussed. Being the competitive market, every industry has to take care of extensive planning and management skills. Mission of the firm should be defined and every person directly or indirectly related to the company should follow the

mission statement. The cost analysis of the project is to be carried out [3].

Lyons, Terry, and Martin Skitmore et.al have proposed the risk management in construction industry. The Queensland construction industry have been considered for study and compared with the other analysis available in the studies presented by other researchers. The risk dealing with the every construction project has different means to be considered. The response and the view of every industry for the risk management plays vital role in reduction of risk i.e. the responding method to the risk decides the damage due to risk. Brain storming is found effective to identify the risk. The project management team has to carry out wide analysis to identify the risk related to the project [4].

Peña-Mora, Feniosky, and Michael Li et.al have discussed dynamic planning and control strategies related to construction industry. The evaluation techniques and dynamic modeling is useful for successful management of project. For fast track projects the dynamic plan is prepared and used. The problems related and forecasted are addressed in early stages of the project. Various proposed techniques are really useful for the timely submission of the construction projects [5].

Chan, Albert PC, David Scott, and Ada PL Chan et.al have proposed the study of various factors affecting the success of construction projects. . Five major groups of independent variables, namely project-related factors, project procedures, project management actions, human-related factors, and external environment are identified as crucial to project success. Authors have presented the overview of the factors after studying the opinions presented by the authors in the reputed journals [6].

CONCLUSION:

Authors have presented the importance of the planning and effective management of the construction project in this paper. According to the problems faced and the solutions proposed by various researchers, its need of time to change the approach for risk management in the construction project. The project managers in this present competent world have to take in to consideration of all the factors affecting the construction projects. The policy makers have to make it mandatory for construction industries to follow the norms. The construction industry has to implement the technologies available to reduce the time required for construction processes. The effective management of the project with proper planning is necessary.

REFERENCES:

- 1) Mansfield, Nigel R., O. O. Ugwu, and T. Doran. "Causes of delay and cost overruns in Nigerian construction projects." *International journal of project Management* 12.4 (1994): 254-260.
- 2) Laufer, Alexander, and Richard L. Tucker. "Is construction project planning really doing its job? A critical examination of focus, role and process." *Construction Management and Economics* 5.3 (1987): 243-266.
- 3) Warszawski, Abraham. "Strategic planning in construction companies." *Journal of construction engineering and management* 122.2 (1996): 133-140.
- 4) Lyons, Terry, and Martin Skitmore. "Project risk management in the Queensland engineering construction industry: a survey." *International journal of project management* 22.1 (2004): 51-61.
- 5) Peña-Mora, Feniosky, and Michael Li. "Dynamic planning and control methodology for design/build fast-track construction projects." *Journal of construction engineering and management* 127.1 (2001): 1-17.
- 6) Chan, Albert PC, David Scott, and Ada PL Chan. "Factors affecting the success of a construction project." *Journal of construction engineering and management* 130.1 (2004): 153-155.
- 7) Laufer, Alexander, and Dora Cohenca. "Factors affecting construction-planning outcomes." *Journal of Construction Engineering and Management* 116.1 (1990): 135-156.
- 8) Hamilton, M. R., and G. Edward Gibson Jr. "Benchmarking pre-project planning effort." *Journal of Management in Engineering* 12.2 (1996): 25-33.
- 9) Edum-Fotwe, Francis T., and Ron Mc Caffer. "Developing project management competency: perspectives from the construction industry." *International Journal of Project Management* 18.2 (2000): 111-124.
- 10) Swarup, P. R. "Indian construction industry." New Delhi, Construction Industry Development Council, New Delhi (2007).
- 11) Rai, Shweta, and Prateek Ghavate "Current infrastructure scenario and rise in construction and allied industries in India."
- 12) Gann, David, and Peter Senker. "Construction skills training for the next millennium." *Construction Management & Economics* 16.5 (1998): 569-580.
- 13) Khakee, Abdul. "Scenario construction for urban planning." *Omega* 19.5 (1991): 459-469.